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ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF INCIDENCE OF VIRAL HEPATITIS B AND C IN UKRAINE DURING 2020–2024

Abstract:

This article analyzes the dynamics of the incidence of viral hepatitis B and C during 2020–2024 in Ukraine. Viral hepatitis B and C remain among the leading global medical and social problems, causing a significant burden of chronic liver diseases, including cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. It is estimated that 2 billion people worldwide have been infected with viral hepatitis, and 350 million suffer from chronic viral hepatitis. Such high prevalence is due to transmission mechanisms, insufficient diagnosis at early stages, limited access to treatment, and a high frequency of comorbid conditions.

Key words: *viral hepatitis B, viral hepatitis C, prevalence, acute course, chronic course, liver cirrhosis*

Introduction: Viral hepatitis B (HBV) and viral hepatitis C (HCV) are dangerous liver diseases caused by viruses: HBV from the Hepadnaviridae family and HCV from the Flaviviridae family, leading to liver inflammation with subsequent development of cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. HBV and HCV occur in acute (up to 6 months) and chronic (more than 6 months) forms.

Materials and Methods: A literature review was conducted based on articles published in PubMed over the past 10 years and official data from the Public Health Center of Ukraine. Current information regarding the dynamics of incidence of viral hepatitis B and C during 2020–2024 in Ukraine was analyzed.

Objective: To analyze scientific publications, literature sources, and official data from the Public Health Center of Ukraine and determine the dynamics of the incidence of viral hepatitis B and C during 2020–2024 in Ukraine.

Relevance: Acute HBV is defined as a discrete onset of symptoms, the presence of jaundice or elevated serum transaminases, and the presence of HBsAg.

Chronic HBV is defined as persistence of hepatitis B surface antigen for more than six months. Individuals with chronic HBV are at risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma and cirrhosis, although mortality decreases with adequate treatment.

Occult HBV infection is another subcategory characterized by detection of HBV DNA with undetectable HBsAg or serological markers of previous viral exposure in plasma.

HBV infection is a serious global public health problem, as 2 billion people worldwide are infected and

350 million suffer from chronic HBV infection. In 2016, global HBsAg positivity was estimated at 3.9%.

HBV infection is the tenth leading cause of death worldwide and results in 500,000 to 1.2 million deaths annually due to chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma; 320,000 people die each year from hepatocellular carcinoma. In Western countries, the disease is relatively rare and usually acquired in adulthood, whereas in Asia and most of Africa, chronic HBV infection is common and infection usually occurs in the perinatal period or early childhood.

In the United States, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), only one-third of patients infected with HBV are aware of their condition. Reasons for low detection and treatment rates include the asymptomatic nature of chronic HBV until late stages, lack of curative therapy of limited duration, complex natural history, and insufficient patient awareness.

Regarding HCV, approximately 71 million people worldwide are chronically infected, of whom 15 million live in Europe. Despite the availability of highly effective direct-acting antiviral therapy, many people remain undiagnosed. It is estimated that only about one-third of chronically infected patients in Europe are aware of their diagnosis. According to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), HCV prevalence in the European Union is 0.5% of the population.

HCV occurs worldwide, with the highest prevalence observed in sub-Saharan Africa, the Eastern Mediterranean, and the Western Pacific regions (5.3%, 4.6%, and 3.9%, respectively). In the United States, approximately 4 million people are chronically infected, with an estimated prevalence among children of 0.2%–

0.4%. Due to the high prevalence, the World Health Organization (WHO) adopted a resolution to improve prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of viral hepatitis. WHO targets include a 65% reduction in liver-related deaths, a 90% reduction in new cases, and diagnosing 90% of people with viral hepatitis by 2030.

Results and Discussion: The aim of our study was to assess the dynamics of the incidence of viral hepatitis from 2020 to 2024. Data were obtained from official sources of the Public Health Center of Ukraine. In 2020, 6.6 thousand cases of total viral hepatitis were registered. In 2021, a decrease was observed: 5.4 thousand cases were registered, which is 22% less than in 2020.

HBV and HCV are transmitted via blood contact, sexual, and vertical routes.

The risk of infection through blood contact, most often during transfusion, depends on the circulating infectious agent, antibodies bound to virions, stage of infection in the donor, volume of blood received, degree of immunosuppression in the recipient, and type of blood product. Mother-to-child transmission remains a global public health problem. If newborns born to HBeAg-positive mothers do not receive hepatitis B immunoglobulin and vaccination shortly after birth, 70%–90% develop HBV infection. If born to HBeAg-negative mothers without prophylaxis, 10%–20% develop infection. Newborns have a 90% probability of developing chronic infection compared to 50% in children under 3 years and 5% in adults after HBV infection.

Historically, men who have sex with men have had the highest risk of HBV infection due to specific sexual practices and higher numbers of partners. HBV and HCV share similarities including global prevalence, transmission routes, hepatotropism, and the ability to cause chronic infection leading to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Dual infection is identified by positive HBsAg and anti-HCV, with viral genome detection needed for confirmation. Since 2022, separate reporting of HBV and HCV has been introduced: 1,416 HBV cases and 3,972 HCV cases were registered in 2022.

In 2023, 2,150 HBV cases were registered (51% more than in 2022) and 6,583 HCV cases (65% more than in 2022).

In 2024, 2,364 HBV cases were registered (9.9% more than in 2023) and 8,031 HCV cases (22% more than in 2023).

Conclusion: Since 2022, Ukraine has observed an increase in newly detected cases of viral hepatitis. In

2023, 51% more HBV cases and 65% more HCV cases were registered compared to 2022. In 2024, 9.9% more HBV cases and 22% more HCV cases were registered compared to 2023.

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